

Effect of Boundary Conditions on the Ballistic Response of Textile Structures

Elvis Cepuš, Ali Shahkarami, Reza Vaziri, and Anoush Poursartip

*Composites Group, Departments of Metals & Materials Engineering and Civil Engineering,
The University of British Columbia, 309-6350 Stores Road, Vancouver, British Columbia,
V6T 1Z4, Canada*
<http://www.composites.ubc.ca>

ABSTRACT

We use a robust high-resolution measurement system for tracking the displacement, velocity and acceleration of a ballistic projectile. In this study, the Enhanced Laser Velocity Sensor (ELVS) is used to characterize the high velocity impact behaviour of Kevlar[®] fabrics. The results are compared with the predictions of a numerical modelling software (TEXIM). The results highlight the critical role played by the boundary conditions on the response of the target. It is shown that prior to failure or perforation the model predicts the response of the fabric fairly well when compared with experimental data. Both correlation and differences are discussed, identifying current model strengths, and needs for future model refinement.

KEYWORDS: ballistic, high-speed data acquisition, enhanced laser velocity sensor (ELVS), dynamic testing, analytical modeling, soft armour, Kevlar fabric.

INTRODUCTION

The need for light and effective protection for defence personnel, law enforcement officers and first-aid workers is significant and increasing. Although new materials and systems are being developed continuously, the design of soft armour is still essentially an empirical exercise. However, our fundamental understanding is improving, experimental techniques are becoming more sophisticated, and modelling capabilities are increasing rapidly. One critical aspect of armour performance is the constraining effect of boundary conditions on the overall performance of the armour. Previous work in the literature either overlooks the boundary condition or typically focuses on a single type of boundary condition within which various fabric systems or projectile geometries with a wide range of impact velocities are studied and compared [1]. The reason boundary conditions are usually not discussed is not due to a lack of interest, but rather due to the limitations of conventional experimental techniques. Normally, there is not enough real-time data during the impact event to be able to evaluate the details of the effect of boundary condition. Generally, one can do no more than determine if a given boundary condition is conducive or detrimental to stopping a given threat.

In this paper the effects of boundary conditions on the ballistic response of a single ply of Kevlar fabric are presented. Through the use of an instrumentation technique that provides details of the fabric response during impact, as well as a numerical model that allows

simulation of the event, the characteristic features of the fabric response under different boundary conditions are identified.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

Apparatus Overview

The ELVS [2-5], shown schematically in Figure 1, uses direct laser-tracking of a projectile to obtain a continuous displacement-time curve through a 1" (25.4 mm) wide window of trajectory. The trajectory window is a stationary flat laser sheet aligned perpendicular to the flight path of the projectile. As the projectile passes through the sheet and exits it, the changing laser-light intensity is recorded and correlated to the projectile position. Successive differentiation of the displacement-time curve yields the projectile instantaneous velocity and acceleration, respectively. From this information, time history curves of energy and impact force are easily obtained.

Figure 1: ELVS Schematic

Experimental Set-up

The UBC powder-gun facilities were used for the ballistic tests reported in this study. The projectiles were 0.22 calibre (5.89 mm diameter) blunt 6061-T6 aluminum cylinders weighing approximately 2.9 grams. The material used was 8428 Kevlar fabric, which is a Kevlar 129 with 840 denier yarns and 28 threads per inch with symmetric warp and weft, cut into square panels. The tests used single ply configurations with 3 different boundary conditions (BCs); fixed-fixed, free-free and fixed-free.

Due to the geometry of the mounting jig, the fixed-fixed and free-free conditions resulted in effective target areas of 9" × 9" (228.6 mm × 228.6 mm) and 13" × 13" (330.2 mm × 330.2 mm), respectively, while the fixed-free effective area was 9" × 13" (228.6 mm × 330.2 mm).

Experimental Results

Figure 2 provides a plot of the energy absorbed by the fabric panel, E_a , as a function of the striking energy, E_s , for the 3 BCs investigated. The overall shapes of these curves are similar to those reported in the literature [e.g. 1] where, typically, the experimental data collected to generate them have included only the projectile striking velocity, V_s , and residual (exit) velocity, V_r . One observation that can be made from these E_a vs E_s curves is that all panels, regardless of their BC, completely absorb the impact energy (as shown by the straight line with a slope of unity) up to a critical point at which the projectile perforates the panel. This critical level of energy, E_c , which corresponds

Figure 2: Energy absorbed as a function of the striking energy for three different boundary conditions.

to the ballistic limit velocity of the fabric, V_c , is strongly dependent on the panel BC. Beyond the critical limit, for all BCs there is a distinct drop in energy absorption, suggesting that at these high levels of energy the fabric panel perforates (fails) in a localized manner. In other words, past E_c the contribution of global (structural) deformation energy to the total absorbed energy is comparatively lower. Therefore, it is not surprising that in the regime where $E_s > E_c$, BCs do not play a significant role in the energy absorption of the panel. It is interesting to note that in all cases the absorbed energy increases again at sufficiently high impact energy levels. The rate of increase of E_a is seen to be almost the same, independent of the BC.

From Figure 2 it appears that a panel with the free-free BC requires more energy to perforate than with fixed-free or fixed-fixed BCs. Therefore, at first sight one might think that a free-free panel would be superior in its protection capability. However, one should also consider the projectile displacement (or the panel deformation) history. In a free-free BC we would expect that a considerable amount of impact energy would be transferred into the kinetic energy associated with the rigid body motion of the panel. For protection purposes it is important that the panel not only absorb the impact energy but in so doing displace as little as possible to minimise the trauma effect. To address this issue and to understand better the partitioning of the impact energy into the kinetic energy and strain energy of the panel, one has to have knowledge of the deformation response of the panel as a function of time. To this end, the ELVS measurement technique allows us to keep track of the projectile position during an impact event. In the following, we will present the effects of BCs on the impact response of Kevlar panels based on the detailed results available from the ELVS.

Figure 3a shows typical projectile velocity versus projectile displacement curves obtained with the ELVS for all three BCs at approximately the same impact velocities. Note that the projectile instantaneous velocity has been normalised with respect to its corresponding striking velocity to facilitate comparison. As expected, under the free-free BC the projectile slows down the least within the acquisition window of the ELVS while the fixed-fixed BC retards the projectile the most.

Figure 3: (a) Normalized projectile velocity and (b) normalized energy absorption versus projectile displacement for a series of non-perforating impact events at similar striking

Figure 3b shows the corresponding curves for the energy absorption by the panel (or energy loss of the projectile) as a function of the projectile displacement. The absorbed energy is normalised with respect to the total incident energy for ease of comparison. It can be seen that the fixed-fixed BC is most effective at absorbing the kinetic energy of the projectile. The amounts of strain energy and kinetic energy absorbed by the panel would require knowledge of the spatial distributions of displacement and velocity. These cannot be assessed from the ELVS data since it only provides information on the time histories of the displacement and velocity at the impact point. In the next section, which is on numerical modelling, the partitioning of the impact energy into the kinetic and strain energies of the panel will be examined with the aid of the computational model, TEXIM.

Figure 3 shows that for the free-free BC, the projectile velocity is reduced by slightly more than 10% before it reaches a constant lower value (and the projectile exits the ELVS measurement window). Figure 4 shows that the mechanism of deformation for a non-perforating test of a panel with free-free BC is that the orthogonal yarns that intersect the impact point tend to unravel and eventually pull out of the panel. A simple kinetic energy balance

suggests that, neglecting frictional effects, the 10% drop in projectile velocity correlates very well with the additional mass of the yarns that engage the projectile and subsequently pull out of the fabric. The mass of the projectile is 2.9 grams, the mass of the engaged yarns is approximately 0.7 grams, and thus the predicted velocity decrease is roughly $1 - \sqrt{2.9 / (2.9 + 0.7)} \approx 10\%$. In contrast, the fixed-fixed panel under a similar non-perforating impact event continues to absorb the impact energy with increasing central displacement and exhibits very different deformation mechanism as shown in Figure 4. For the panel with fixed-free BCs, the fixed yarns prevent the free orthogonal yarns from pulling out, and therefore the response of such panels is expectedly closer to that of the fixed-fixed panels. The ELVS results shown in Figure 3 clearly support this argument.

Figure 4: Post-mortem photographs of a panel with free-free and fixed-fixed boundary conditions struck just below E_c , showing the different deformation mechanisms.

NUMERICAL MODEL

A numerical model, TEXIM [3], has been developed to simulate impact of a blunt cylindrical projectile on a rectangular multi-layer fabric under different boundary conditions. The basic concept underlying the numerical model is an extension of the original approach by Roylance [6,7], which models the fabric as an assembly of nodal masses and string elements. These nodal masses represent the areal density (inertia) of the fabric while the strings represent the elastic properties (stiffness) of the fabric. Every internal mass has four strings attached to it and has three translational degrees of freedom with reference to the x , y , and z co-ordinate system. Figure 5 shows a generic nodal mass m , subjected to a set of internal forces from the surrounding strings.

Figure 5: A schematic of the mass-string model showing a nodal mass under a set of forces from neighbouring strings.

The mathematical formulation of the model is based on the conservation of momentum in the system. By enforcing the impulse-momentum balance at nodal points of the mass-string system the nodal co-ordinates of the masses are updated at every time step and the current state of strain in each string is evaluated. Finally, the forces in the strings are computed from the strains and strain rates using a linear visco-elastic constitutive model.

Effect of Boundary Conditions

Parallel to the experimental effort, panels with different boundary conditions were modelled using TEXIM. The deformed shape of the fabric and propagation of the strain waves were computed at different time-steps. Figure 6 shows a snap-shot comparison between the deformed geometry of a single layer of Kevlar fabric with free-free and fixed-fixed boundary conditions 100 μ s after impact by a blunt cylindrical projectile (5.59 mm diameter, and weighing 2.9 g) with a striking velocity of 167 m/s. As can be seen, in the fabric panel with free boundaries the orthogonal fibres that pass through the impact zone have moved in-plane

Figure 6: Computed deformation profiles of the fabric panel with (a) free-free and (b) fixed-fixed boundary conditions 100 μ s after impact by a projectile with a striking velocity of 167 m/s.

towards the impact point. This is in keeping with the experimental observations shown in Figure 4. Also, the size of the deformation cone is relatively small with steep slopes on the sides. On the other hand, restraining the fibres at the ends as in the case where the boundaries are fixed results in smaller in-plane displacement of the fibres. This influences the size and the shape of the deformation cone making it bigger or more spread out than the free-free case and with a milder slope.

Table 1: Computed instantaneous values of the projectile velocity and displacement, as well as the strain and kinetic energies of the fabric panel 100 ms after impact by a projectile with an initial striking velocity of 167 m/s.

Boundary Condition	Current Velocity [m/s]	Projectile Displacement [mm]	Strain Energy [J]	Kinetic Energy Out-of-plane [J]	Kinetic Energy In-plane [J]	Total Absorbed Energy [J]
Fixed-Fixed	82.6	13.77	17.02	14.12	0.18	31.3
Free-Free	152.6	16.00	0.03	2.10	4.66	6.8

The energy components of these two panels as calculated by TEXIM are summarised in Table 1. It can be seen that at a given time and for identical impact conditions, the fixed-fixed panel absorbs more energy compared to the free-free panel. The numerical results show that in the free-free panel, the absorbed energy is mainly stored in the form of kinetic energy, both in the out-of-plane and in-plane motion of the fabric. The strain energy of the free-free panel is negligible compared to the fixed-fixed panel, in which the fibres carry more than half of the absorbed energy in the form of strain energy. The remainder of the absorbed energy in the fixed-fixed panel is embedded in the out-of-plane motion of the deformation cone. Owing to its immovable boundaries, there is very little kinetic energy associated with the in-plane motion of the fixed-fixed panel.

NUMERICAL PREDICTIONS VS. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to compare the numerical results with the experimental data, the free-free and fixed-fixed panels that were discussed in the experimental section were also modelled using TEXIM. The actual effective sizes of the panels were modelled in each case, i.e. 9" × 9"

Figure 7: Comparison between the predicted and measured (a) normalized projectile velocity and (b) normalized energy absorption versus projectile displacement for a series of non-perforating impact events at similar striking velocities.

(228.6 mm × 228.6 mm) and 13" × 13" (330.2 mm × 330.2 mm), for the fixed-fixed and free-free panels, respectively. Figure 7a shows a comparison between the numerically predicted and experimentally measured projectile velocity versus projectile displacement curves for two non-perforating impact events. The instantaneous velocities are normalised with respect to the striking velocity to facilitate comparison of response trends. Figure 7b shows the corresponding plots of the energy absorbed versus projectile displacement. As discussed above, it is apparent that for a given incident impact energy the fixed-fixed panel absorbs more energy than its free-free counterpart. Although the numerical model does not consistently match the experimental measurements in an absolute sense, it captures the observed trends extremely well. Overall, the model better predicts the response of the free-free panel. In the fixed-fixed case the model over-predicts the rate of absorption of energy as measured by the slope of the curves in Figure 7b. This finding is not surprising given that the model assumes a theoretical end fixity that cannot be fully realised experimentally. In the experiment there is bound to be some degree of slippage and in-plane fibre movement at the boundaries of the support fixture that is difficult to model.

The points labelled *A* and *B* in Figure 7 correspond to the instant when the longitudinal strain waves that were initiated at the impact point have returned back to the impact point after being reflected from the boundaries. The reason why the points *A* and *B* do not coincide stems from the fact that the strain waves travel different distances in each case (note that the effective panel size in the free-free case is greater).

One of the advantages that a numerical model offers is that it can provide detailed quantitative information on the spatial and temporal distribution of such local variables as strain or stress, which often reveal important attributes of the response. For example, for the two impact conditions modelled above, Figure 8 shows the predicted evolution of the strain in the string element that intersects the periphery of the projectile (see the inset). Just as in Figure 7, point *A* in Figure 8 corresponds to the condition when the reflected strain wave has just returned to the string that is being monitored. Beyond point *A* it can be seen that the strain either magnifies or diminishes depending on whether the panel *BC* is fixed or free, respectively. As a consequence, for a given displacement of the projectile, the fixed-fixed panel develops more strain and thus absorbs more strain energy than the free-free panel.

From Figure 8 it can be seen that there is considerable jitter in the predicted strains for the fixed-fixed BC. This jitter arises directly from the explicit numerical algorithm used to perform the time integrations in TEXIM. This is a common phenomenon that occurs when we compute instantaneous values of stresses and strains in impact events. Introducing some form of artificial viscosity or damping can often attenuate these spurious numerical oscillations. Although the constitutive model used in TEXIM includes a viscous term, the viscosity parameter was not activated in the numerical results presented here.

Figure 8: Predicted evolution of strain in the string element shown in the inset, as a function of the projectile displacement for the fixed-fixed and free-free boundary conditions.

One of the implications of the numerical noise, in which the amplitude of the strain repeatedly grows and decays, is that if a failure criterion based on the instantaneous value of the strain is employed then the critical value of strain can potentially be reached prematurely. This has to be taken into account when formulating a suitable failure criterion to signal the perforation of the fabric.

CONCLUSIONS

The study presented here shows the significant effects of boundary conditions on the energy absorption mechanisms, and subsequent ballistic performance of fabric structures. Fixed-fixed boundaries promote a more rapid development of strain energy within the fabric and an increase in strain localisation, with relatively small panel deformation prior to complete impact energy absorption or failure. Free-free boundaries are more likely to promote gross translation of impact energy into kinetic energy of the panel with relatively little strain localisation and failure. The current version of the numerical model accurately predicts the trends and instantaneous values of the projectile velocity and energy absorption by the panel. However, the predictive capability of this model needs to be further enhanced by incorporation of realistic failure criteria that account for conditions that lead to the failure (perforation) of the fabric during impact.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the valuable input of Mr. Roger Soar and Mr. Ian Swan of the Pacific Safety Products (PSP), Inc., Kelowna, and Mr. Gilles Pageau of the Defence Research Establishment Valcartier (DREV), Québec. We would also like to thank Ms. Darlene Starratt and Mr. Roger Bennett of the UBC Composites Group for helping with the experimental work as well as previous members of the group, Dr. Nabil Abdel-Rahman and Dr. Yuangao Zhang for their efforts in numerical software development. The financial support provided by DREV, PSP and the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NSERC) of Canada through the Strategic Grant No. STR192906, is also gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. P.M. Cunniff, *An Analysis of the System Effects in Woven Fabrics Under Ballistic Loading*, Textile Research Journal, 62(9), 495-509, 1992.
2. D. Starratt, T. Sanders, E. Cepuš, A. Poursartip, and R. Vaziri, *An Efficient Method for Continuous Measurement of Projectile Motion in Ballistic Impact Experiments*, International Journal for Impact Engineering, Submitted June 1998.
3. N. Abdel-Rahman, D. Starratt, G. Pageau, Y. Zhang, R. Vaziri, and A. Poursartip, *Experimental and Theoretical Investigation of the Ballistic Impact of Textile Materials*, Personal Armour Systems Symposium 1998, 213-222, Colchester, UK, September 1998.
4. D. Starratt, *An Instrumented Experimental Study of the Ballistic Response of Textile Materials*, University of British Columbia M.A.Sc. Thesis, 1998.
5. T. Sanders, *Penetration of Composite Laminates by Conical Indenters and Projectiles*, University of British Columbia M.A.Sc. Thesis, 1997.

6. J. Ting, D. Roylance, C.H. Chi, B. Chitrangad, *Numerical Modeling of Fabric Panel Response to Ballistic Impact*, 25th International SAMPE Technical Conference, October 26-28, 1993, 384-392.
7. V.P.W. Shim, V.B.C. Tan, and T.E. Tay, "**Modelling Deformation and Damage Characteristics of Woven Fabric Under Small Projectile Impact**", International Journal of Impact Engineering, Volume 16, Number 4, 1995, p.p. 585-605.